

Reference

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PROGRESS REPORT UNOE Student Fellows Project Mexico Team

Title of the Project:	UNOE Student Fellows Project
Host Institution:	Benemérita Escuela Normal de Coahuila (Mexico)
Date of establishment of Project/Network:	January 2026
Period of activity under report:	January 2026-June 2026
Report established by:	María Soledad Ramírez-Montoya (<i>Chair UNESCO</i>) <i>Technical project manager Mexico Team</i>
Project Team:	Gabriela Alvarado Alonzo (Student) Yaretzy Gabriela Calamaco Munguía (Student) Yovanna Karime Leija Rodríguez (Student) Ruth Montes Martínez (Professor) Isolda Margarita Castillo Martínez (Professor) Arlene Guadalupe Portugal Toro (Professor)

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1. Executive Summary:

Objectives and results of the Project team

UNOE Student Fellows Project aims to build a global community of students from different countries where our Chairs are located (Global North and South), so they can participate in debates and propose visions related to the future of advanced technologies in education and the role of "openness" in higher education.

In this project, the **Mexican Team** aims to create opportunities for the exchange of experiences among university students, perspectives and best practices among educators from different countries, fostering international collaboration and mutual learning for the projection of open education.

- **Objective 1:**

To develop a TikTok profile as a digital outreach and engagement platform aimed at connecting with students from Escuelas Normales across Mexico, fostering discussion and participation on the project's key topics, and gathering their perspectives, experiences, and insights regarding the educational, ethical, and academic challenges faced in contemporary higher education contexts.

Results:

Appendix 1: Tiktok profile

- **Objective 2:**

To develop an interactive digital platform that promotes global collaboration and professional learning among teachers by enabling the exchange of successful classroom practices through multimedia resources such as short videos, audio recordings, and infographics, fostering the sharing of educational experiences across different countries, educational levels, and teaching topics.

Results:

Appendix 2: World Map Teaching Practices

- **Objective 3:**

To strengthen students' research, academic communication, and professional development skills through the preparation of an academic seminar based on their thesis that reflects their experiences, motivations, and learning throughout the program, promoting knowledge dissemination and active participation in academic and research communities.

Results:

Appendix 3: Proceedings TEEM Conference

- **Objective 4:**

To create a debate panel that promotes the exchange of perspectives among participants from different countries regarding the use of artificial intelligence and open educational resources, encouraging intercultural dialogue, collaborative learning, and the sharing of innovative practices and challenges within diverse educational systems.

Results:

Appendix 4: Proposal UNESCO workshop

- **Objective 5:**

To strengthen critical thinking regarding artificial intelligence in education through the production of reflective texts for the UNOE blog, supported by a guide that scaffolds both the writing process and conceptual development within the project framework.

Results:

Appendix 5: Astonishment report

2. Activities

Overview of activities undertaken by the Project Team during the reporting period

Research activities:

The project aims to examine, through non-experimental quantitative methods, the role of open educational resources and artificial intelligence in contemporary education among higher education students, specifically future teachers, analyzing their influence on teaching and learning processes, the promotion of ethical values, the improvement of educational accessibility and innovation, and their contribution to reducing academic stress and enhancing students' overall academic experience.

The instruments were the following:

AI-ED-SAT to collect and analyze information regarding participants' knowledge, perceptions, and use of artificial intelligence in educational contexts, identifying its influence on teaching and learning practices, academic activities, and the integration of technological tools in education (Sartor-Harad & Azevedo Gomes, 2024).

Results:

Appendix 6: Analysis of results AI-ED-SAT

Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress to identify and analyze the frequency of academic stressors, as well as the physical, psychological, and behavioral reactions and coping mechanisms experienced (Barraza-Macías, 2018)

Results:

Appendix 7: Analysis of results Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress

e-Open for assessing open education competencies, an instrument designed within the framework of UNESCO recommendations (Ramírez-Montoya & Tenorio-Sepúlveda, 2021).

Results:

Appendix 8: Analysis of results e-Open for assessing open education competencies

Measure the Academic Use of Generative AI in University Students (Trejo-Trejo & Gordillo-Espinoza, n.d.).

Results:

Appendix 9: Analysis of results Academic use of Generative AI

The population was composed of 100 higher education students enrolled from the first to the fourth year of their academic programs, all of whom are future teachers in training. A quantitative methodological approach was employed throughout the study to collect and analyze data related to the research objectives.

Statistical analyses were carried out using the results obtained from the applied instruments in order to identify patterns, relationships, and trends associated with the studied variables (use of AI, academic stress, resources of open education). The quantitative data allowed for the examination of participants' perspectives, experiences, and competencies related to the topics.

This research carefully considered ethical aspects related to data protection, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants, as well as respect for autonomy, diversity, values, and human dignity. Furthermore, the study was conducted with honesty and academic integrity throughout the processes of data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

a) Education/Training <i>Key education programmes and training delivered and research undertaken by the project team during the reporting period, target group and geographical coverage.</i>	
Education (leading to certificate)	<p>The project team participated in educational and academic training activities focused on artificial intelligence, open education, digital technologies, and teacher training.</p> <p>Building on this foundation, the Mexican students on the project team—alongside teams from other countries—will deliver a webinar series to discuss open education and artificial intelligence.</p> <p>Objective: To foster a global and intercultural dialogue space where students critically analyze the future of education by examining the challenges of the ethical use of artificial intelligence and the integration of open educational resources across different countries, comparing various educational support systems in order to propose collective solutions that transform higher education learning environments.</p> <p>This program will award a micro-certification to participants and will take place during the project's next phase.</p> <p>Results: Appendix 10: Webinar Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future</p>

b) Products Summary <i>Major publications and teaching/learning materials</i>																					
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c) Tiktok Page <i>(any other activities to report)</i>
<p>TiktokPage https://www.tiktok.com/@unoe.mexico.team?r=1&t=ZS-96hc1xQBERg Appendix 1: Tiktok profile</p>

3. Future Plans and Development Prospects:

Outline of action plan for the next biennium and short/medium and long-term development prospects. Please do not hesitate to refer to difficulties that the Chair has experienced.
(Not exceeding 300 words)

In line with the general objective of the UNOE project, the activities are:

- Visits and webinars with participating Chairs and organizations leading youth-focused educational projects (Learning Planet Institute, UNESCO SDG4 Youth Group, GO-GN).
- Online presentations and discussions on the future of higher education.
- Student participation in conferences to present findings.
- Visits and technical exchanges to share experiences.
- Creation and publication of outputs (documents, reports, websites, collages) and a final open-access book summarizing the experience.

The following actions will focus on continuing the dissemination of educational content through UNOE blog and TikTok by regularly uploading videos that introduce and promote new educational resources, innovative teaching strategies, and emerging technological tools related to artificial intelligence and education. These activities aim to strengthen interaction with students and future teachers, encourage participation in academic discussions, and expand access to accessible and meaningful learning opportunities within digital environments:

June 2026: **Webinar Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future**. This proposal consists of an interactive webinar series (three sessions of one hour 9:00-10:00am) designed to promote dialogue, collaboration, and the exchange of perspectives among participants from different educational and cultural contexts. The invited participants will be international guests and members of the UNOE program, attendees will answer three reflective questions during each session (certificates of participation will be awarded to those who successfully attend and participate in all three webinars).

Schedule of Sessions:

June 13, 2026- Innovating Education with AI and OER.

Speakers:

- Yaretzy Calamaco Benemerita Escuela Normal de Coahuila (Mexico)
- Angustina Mignaco. Universidad de la República (Uruguay)

June 20, 2026- Fair and Ethical use of Artificial Intelligence in Assessment.

Speakers:

- Yovanna Lejja (Benemerita Escuela Normal de Coahuila, Mexico)
- Lucky Geluk (University of Cape Town South Africa)
- Colyne Souriau (Nantes Université France)
- Hiba Haj Mahmoud (Univ of Sousse Tunisia)

June 27, 2026- Motivations for learning and AI influence.

Speakers:

- Gabriela Alvarado Benemerita Escuela Normal de Coahuila (Mexico)
- Lucía Lanza: Universidad de la República (Uruguay)
- Rebeca Mesquita: Universidad de Brasilia (Brasil)

June 2026: **“Living Museum”**. Will be coordinated with undergraduate students from a teacher education institution. Participants will share images from their teaching practice that reflect positive aspects and challenges of the teaching profession, encouraging reflection and dialogue about their experiences in educational settings. The contributions will be collected and displayed through Mentimeter to create a collaborative visual space. Additionally, international peers from the UNOE program will participate through brief interventions, sharing perspectives about the educational systems and teaching experiences in their countries, promoting intercultural exchange and global learning.

Tentative date: Last week of June

International events in the coming months where instruments and strategies to collect project data will be applied are as follows:

(a) Digital Learning Week (September 2026)

(b) TEEM 2026 (October 2026)

International placements will promote academic actions such as article writing, fundraising, collaborative academic events (e.g., bootcamp, conferences, implementation of fieldwork, etc.).

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Tiktok profile

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 1: Tik Tok profile
Products, outcomes or milestones	Technical report by section. Tik Tok videos.
Name	Appendix 1: Tik Tok profile
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yaretzy Calamaco and Yovanna Leija
Objective	Objective 1: To diagnose training practices that promote complex thinking in institutions and other national and international educational entities through a comparative analysis of their programs and alternative professionalizing credentials.

Support evidence:

TiktokPage

<https://www.tiktok.com/@unoe.mexico.team? r=1& t=ZS-96hc1xQBERg>

Appendix 2 - World Map Teaching Practices

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 2: World Map Teaching Practices
Products, outcomes or milestones	Map with collaborative opinions of open education and use of AI
Name	Appendix 2: World Map Teaching Practices
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yarety Calamaco and Yovanna Leija
Objective	Objective 2: To develop an interactive digital platform that promotes global collaboration and professional learning among teachers by enabling the exchange of successful classroom practices through multimedia resources such as short videos, audio recordings, and infographics, fostering the sharing of educational experiences across different countries, educational levels, and teaching topics.

NOTE: The support evidence is currently awaiting international collaboration confirmation from members of the UNOE program, whose participation will contribute to strengthening intercultural dialogue and the exchange of educational perspectives.

Support evidence:

Appendix 3: Proceedings TEEM Conference

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 3 - Proceedings TEEM Conference
Products, outcomes or milestones	Development of the seminar draft, including the definition of topics, structure, and collaborative planning of activities.
Name	Proceedings TEEM Conference
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yaretzy Calamaco, Yovanna Leija
Objective	Objective 3: To collaboratively design and organize the seminar structure and contents related to the project topics.

Support evidence:

Three procedures for a congress indexed in Scopus and where recognition is given to the project

Artificial intelligence and metacognitive strategies in the face of academic stress at university: A descriptive correlational study

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Abstract. The use of Artificial Intelligence in education could serve as a means to reduce stress when integrated as support for students' needs. This study aimed to analyze the relationship between the use of Artificial Intelligence as a tool and its impact on the reduction of academic stress. The research was conducted using a quantitative methodological approach with a non-experimental design and an explanatory-correlational scope. Data collection was carried out using two instruments: the second version of the Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress to specifically assess academic stress, and the AI-ED-SAT instrument to analyze competencies related to AI use. Both instruments were administered to a sample of 100 pre-service teachers. The findings revealed: (a) a moderate level of knowledge and use of AI, (b) difficulties in the application of metacognitive strategies for reducing academic stress, and (c) associations between AI use and students' academic and emotional aspects. The study contributes to highlighting the need to strengthen digital and socio-emotional competencies while providing useful evidence for the design of training programs and future educational interventions. Furthermore, the findings suggest that AI may function not only as a technological resource, but also as a support tool that promotes organization, access to information, and strategies associated with coping with academic demands.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Academic Stress, Higher Education, Educational Innovation, Competencies, Pre-service Teachers

Acknowledgments

This study is part of the UNOE Student Fellows Project, funded by The Hewlett Foundation and coordinated by the University of Nantes. We are grateful for the opportunity to participate in this program, which promotes research related to emerging technologies in the field of education. We would also like to thank the Benemérita Escuela Normal de Coahuila for its support and for fostering the academic and research training that made this study possible.

Ethical Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence Among University Students: A Descriptive-Correlational Study

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Abstract. The incorporation of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) into higher education has transformed teaching and learning processes by facilitating access to information, content creation, and academic support. However, its use also raises ethical challenges related to academic integrity, digital responsibility, and critical thinking. The objective of this study was to analyze the perceptions of preservice primary education teachers regarding the ethical use of generative artificial intelligence in academic contexts. A quantitative research approach was adopted, employing a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational design. Data were collected through a Likert-scale questionnaire administered to a sample of 56 undergraduate students enrolled in a teacher education institution in northern Mexico. The results revealed: (a) a generally favorable perception of generative artificial intelligence, highlighting high levels of self-efficacy and its frequent integration into academic activities such as information retrieval, content creation, and study support; (b) areas for improvement related to ethical use, risk awareness, potential technological dependency, and reflection on social and environmental impacts; and (c) a positive relationship between perceived self-efficacy and the ethical use of artificial intelligence. This study contributes by identifying both strengths and areas for improvement in the use of generative artificial intelligence among preservice teachers, emphasizing the need to strengthen critical digital literacy and ethical training in order to promote the responsible use of generative artificial intelligence in higher education.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence, Higher Education, Digital Ethics, Student Perceptions, Competence, Educational Innovation.

Acknowledgments. This study was conducted within the framework of the UNOE Student Fellows Project, funded by The Hewlett Foundation and coordinated through the University of Nantes. The authors gratefully acknowledge the support provided for research on emerging technologies in education. The authors also extend their appreciation to the Benemérita Escuela Normal de Coahuila for its valuable support, which was essential to the development of this research.

Toward Open and Inclusive Teacher Education in Artificial Intelligence Environments: A Cross-Sectional Descriptive Correlational Study

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¹María-Soledad Ramírez- Montoya ¹[0000-0002-1274-706X]

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Abstract. The expansion of artificial intelligence and digital learning ecosystems has transformed the ways in which knowledge is accessed and distributed in higher education. This study aims to identify open education competencies that support inclusive access to knowledge within artificial intelligence-enabled learning environments among higher education students enrolled in teacher education programs. The study adopted a quantitative approach, with a non-experimental design and a descriptive scope. Data were collected using the e-Open instrument, designed to measure open education competencies in accordance with UNESCO recommendations. The sample consisted of 50 pre-service teachers. The findings revealed: (a) a moderate level of open education competencies; (b) strengths in the use of digital tools and open educational resources; (c) a positive perception of inclusive practices and the democratization of knowledge; (d) limitations in competencies related to sustainability and the financing of educational projects; (e) limited proficiency in the application of open licenses and regulatory frameworks; and (f) a need to strengthen international collaboration and competencies related to open access to knowledge. This research contributes to ongoing discussions on digital inclusion, open education, and teacher education within educational ecosystems mediated by artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Open Education, Artificial Intelligence, Inclusive Access to Knowledge, Teacher Education, Higher Education, Educational Innovation

Acknowledgments

This study was conducted within the framework of the UNOE Student Fellows Project, funded by the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation and coordinated by the University of Nantes. The authors gratefully acknowledge the support provided to advance educational research and innovation through emerging technologies. The authors also extend their appreciation to the Benemérita Escuela Normal de Coahuila for its institutional support and commitment to promoting the development of research competencies.

Appendix 4: Proposal UNESCO workshop

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 4: Proposal UNESCO workshop
Products, outcomes or milestones	Research and collaborative activities
Name	Appendix 4: Proposal UNESCO workshop
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yaretzy Calamaco, Yovanna Leija, Ruth Montes, Isolda Castillo, Arlene Portugal, Maria Soledad Ramírez-Montoya, Rebecca Araujo, Juan Bentancor, Lucía Lanza
Objective	To create a debate panel that promotes the exchange of perspectives among participants from different countries regarding the use of artificial intelligence and open educational resources, encouraging intercultural dialogue, collaborative learning, and the sharing of innovative practices and challenges within diverse educational systems.

Support evidence:

Confirmation of receipt and proposal

Session title: AI skills among the next generation of students: Horizons for ethics and open education

Submission category: Surprise us — Do you have something else in mind?

What if the most pressing voices missing from global discussions on artificial intelligence (AI) and education policy are those closest to the classroom? This session brings together five young researchers in higher education at the heart of Digital Learning Week 2026, as student fellows of the Unitwin Network on Open Education (UNOE) and as knowledge producers whose empirical work directly addresses the Facts, Frictions and Frontiers shaping education in the age of AI.

In an environment where data floods theoretical publications and students' presence in the classroom is merely a figment of the imagination, this session offers something rare: real evidence, generated by students, about students, for policy-making. Five original research studies by UNOE fellows, based on UNESCO's AI competency frameworks and open education principles, are presented through a Living Research Gallery, a format that reimagines academic exchange. Instead of a traditional panel, participants navigate simultaneous research stations, interacting directly with each young researcher in rotating 8-minute dialogues, before coming together for a 20-minute collective synthesis. The result is not a presentation to watch, but a conversation to participate in.

Your Digital Learning Week 2026 presentation proposal has been received

UNESCO Digital Learning Week <noreply@alchemer.com>

Today at 8:57 p.m.

To: solramirez2009@gmail.com

Thank you for your interest in presenting during Digital Learning Week 2026.

Proposals will be reviewed by UNESCO and decision notifications will be sent by end of June 2026.

If you have not already registered to attend the event, please go to our website and register now. Registration is required of all participants including presenters.

To learn more about Digital Learning Week 2026, please visit: <https://www.unesco.org/en/weeks/digital-learning>

Should you have any questions, please email dlw@unesco.org.

Appendix 5: Astonishment report

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 5: Astonishment report
Products, outcomes or milestones	Blog article
Name	Appendix 5: Astonishment report
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yaretzy Calamaco, Yovanna Leija
Objective	To establish an effective communication channel among all fellows in order to promote the exchange of experiences, ideas, and perspectives related to the educational systems of their respective countries. This space will encourage collaborative learning, intercultural dialogue, and the sharing of good practices, challenges, and innovative strategies that contribute to a deeper understanding of education in different national contexts

Support evidence:

Deliverable “Los Protocolos de Convivencia y Seguridad Escolar como Parte del Sistema Educativo Mexicano”

“Los Protocolos de Convivencia y Seguridad Escolar como Parte del Sistema Educativo Mexicano”

Los protocolos de convivencia y seguridad escolar forman parte esencial del Sistema Educativo Mexicano y representan un elemento clave para garantizar ambientes de aprendizaje sanos, seguros y propicios para el desarrollo integral de los estudiantes. Más allá de ser un conjunto de normas o lineamientos, estos protocolos representan una herramienta fundamental que guía la actuación de toda la comunidad educativa ante diversas situaciones, desde conflictos cotidianos hasta emergencias de mayor gravedad.

Es importante mencionar que los protocolos no solo tienen una función reactiva, es decir, no únicamente sirven cuando ocurre un problema; por el contrario, su existencia permite prevenir situaciones de riesgo, promover la convivencia pacífica y fortalecer valores como el respeto, la empatía y la responsabilidad. Considero que son uno de los elementos más valiosos dentro de la nueva normatividad escolar y se deberían preservar y adaptar a las nuevas necesidades, emergencias y eventos que se presenten en la vida docente.

Educar en tiempos de atención fragmentada

Figura 1. Estudiantes de educación primaria utilizando iPads para desarrollar proyectos escolares. Fotografía tomada por Lexie Flickinger y publicada por Brad Flickinger en School Technology. Licencia Creative Commons Attribution 2.0 (CC BY 2.0). Disponible en: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/56155476@N08/6659992055>

Por Yaretzy Gabriela Calamaco Munguía

En una época caracterizada por la conectividad permanente y el acceso inmediato a la información, surge una pregunta que no deja de sorprenderme: ¿cómo educar cuando la atención se encuentra constantemente dividida entre múltiples estímulos?

Lo que me asombra no es que los estudiantes utilicen tecnología. Tampoco que pasen gran parte de su tiempo frente a pantallas. Lo que realmente llama mi atención es la facilidad con la que pueden concentrarse durante horas en determinados contenidos digitales y, al mismo tiempo, la dificultad que muchas veces experimentan para mantener la atención en actividades escolares más tradicionales.

La ética académica en tiempos de inteligencia artificial

Autor:

Yovanna Leija estudia la Maestría en Innovación Pedagógica y Gestión Educativa en la Benemérita Escuela Normal de Coahuila, en México. Se interesa por la investigación educativa, especialmente en temas relacionados con inteligencia artificial, ética y aprendizaje. Disfruta analizar los desafíos actuales del sistema educativo y reflexionar sobre las transformaciones que las nuevas tecnologías generan en la enseñanza y el aprendizaje.

Imagen:

Appendix 6: Analysis of results of the instrument AI-ED-SAT

Sartor-Harada, A., Azevedo Gomes, J.: AI-ED-SAT: Diseño y validación de un cuestionario para autoevaluar competencias docentes en IA educativa. Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia (RIED) (2024). <https://revistas.uned.es/index.php/ried/article/view/45413/33458>

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 6: Analysis of results AI-ED-SAT
Products, outcomes or milestones	Research activities: Instrument application
Name	Appendix 6: Analysis of results AI-ED-SAT
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado
Research activities:	The instrument was applied to 100 students from first to fourth year of the Teaching degree to collect and analyze information regarding participants' knowledge, perceptions, and use of artificial intelligence in educational contexts, identifying its influence on teaching and learning practices, academic activities, and the integration of technological tools in education

Support evidence:

Analysis per item

Dimensiones	Indicadores	Media
Conocimientos generales sobre la IA y su aplicación educativa	1. Conocimiento general de la IA y sus aplicaciones	3.79
	2. Comprensión del impacto de la IA en la educación	4.02
	3. Identificación de herramientas de IA educativas	3.85
	4. Familiarización con conceptos clave de IA	3.17
	5. Comprensión de fundamentos de la IA	2.98
	6. Diferenciación de tipos de IA en educación	3.65
	7. Capacidad de explicación básica de la IA	3.87
	8. Conocimiento de ejemplos de IA educativa	3.7
	9. Análisis de ventajas y limitaciones de la IA	3.99
	10. Investigación sobre tendencias de IA en educación	3.34
Uso pedagógico de herramientas de IA	11. Integración de IA en la práctica	3.89
	12. Diseño de actividades con IA	3.77
	13. Conocimiento de plataformas de IA educativa	3.61
	14. Evaluación del impacto de la IA en el aprendizaje	3.47
	15. Generación de materiales didácticos con IA	3.42
	16. Uso de asistentes virtuales en la enseñanza	2.76
	17. Evaluación automatizada mediante IA	2.93
	18. Exploración de IA para aprendizaje adaptativo	3.19
Ética y consideraciones sobre IA en el aula	19. Integración de la IA en el trabajo colaborativo	3.36
	20. Formación continua en IA educativa	2.99
	21. Conciencia de sesgos en la IA	3.91
	22. Promoción del uso ético de la IA	3.73
	23. Enseñanza de la privacidad y seguridad de la IA	3.32
	24. Reflexión sobre ética y automatización educativa	3.65
	25. Análisis de la influencia de la IA en decisiones	3.77
	26. Discusión sobre transparencia algorítmica	3.13
	27. Identificación del impacto social de la IA	3.61
	28. Fomento del uso equitativo de la IA	3.35
Integración curricular de la IA	29. Investigación sobre normativas de IA en educación	3.09
	30. Reflexión sobre el impacto social de la IA	3.2
	31. Integración de la IA en la planificación curricular	3.5
	32. Diseño de estrategias didácticas con IA	3.4
	33. Conocimiento de marcos curriculares con IA	2.71
	34. Formación en IA aplicada a la enseñanza	2.95
	35. Desarrollo de proyectos interdisciplinarios con IA	3.17
	36. Uso de simulaciones educativas con IA	3.08
	37. Colaboración docente para integrar IA	2.89
	38. Investigación de metodologías activas con IA	2.57
39. Diseño de unidades didácticas basadas en IA	2.85	
40. Promoción de la alfabetización en IA	2.85	
	Media general	3.362
	Desviación estándar	0.3966
	Límite inferior	2.9653
	Límite superior	3.7586

Appendix 7: Analysis of results of the instrument Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress

Barraza-Macías, A.: Inventario sistémico cognoscitivista para el estudio del estrés académico: SISCO SV-21. ECORFAN México (2018). <https://upd.edu.mx/PDF/Libros/Estres.pdf>

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 7: Analysis of results Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress
Products, outcomes or milestones	Research activities: Instruments application
Name	Appendix 7: Analysis of results Cognitive Inventory of Academic Stress
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado Alonzo
Research activities	The instrument was applied to 100 students from first to fourth year of the Teaching degree to identify and analyze the frequency of academic stressors, as well as the physical, psychological, and behavioral reactions and coping mechanisms experienced

Support evidence:

Analysis per item

Dimensiones	Indicadores	Media
Estresores	1.Comparación con sus pares	2.89
	2.Responsabilidad personal por cumplir con actividades	2.57
	3.Sobrecarga de tareas y trabajos	4.09
	4.Personalidad y carácter del docente	3.6
	5.Exigencia de docente	3.95
	6.Tipo de evaluación	3.54
	7.Naturaleza del trabajo (trabajo, ensayo, mapas conceptuales)	3.6
	8.Comprensión del contenido	3.95
	9.Tiempo limitado para terminar trabajos	4.05
	10.Insomnia o pesadillas	3.09
	11.Cansancio permanente	3.33
	12.Dolor de cabeza o migraña	3.48
	13.Problemas de digestión	3.09
	14.Rascarse, morderse las uñas, frotarse	3.33
	15.Somnolencia	3.48
Síntomas	16.Incapacidad de relajarse	3.13
	17.Sentimientos de depresión y tristeza	2.64
	18.Ansiedad o desesperación	3.36
	19. Problemas de concentración	3.46
	20. Sensación de mente vacía	3.1
	21. Problemas de memoria	3.2
	22. Agresividad o irritabilidad	2.81
	23.Tendencia a discutir	2.71
	24. Aislamiento	2.52
	25. Desgano para labores escolares	3.11
	26. Ausentismo de clase	2.29
Estrategias de afrontamiento	27. Aumento o reducción de consumo de alimentos	3.14
	28. Habilidad asertiva	3.1
	29.Elaboración de un plan para ejecución de tareas	2.29
	30. Emplear el sentido del humor	3.14
	31. Elogios a sí mismo	3.1
	32. Distracción evasiva	3.21
	33. Religiosidad	2.54
	34. Búsqueda de información sobre la situación	2.78
	35. Verbalización de la situación que preocupa	3.28
		Media general
	Desviación estándar	0.4645
	Límite inferior	2.7054
	Límite superior	3.6345

Appendix 8: Analysis of results e-Open for assessing open education competencies

Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. & Tenorio-Sepúlveda, G.C. (2021). Instrumento e-Open: Medición de competencias de educación abierta Diseñado en el marco de las recomendaciones UNESCO [Instrumento]. Retrieved from: <https://repositorio.tec.mx/handle/11285/639413>.

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 8: Analysis of results e-Open for assessing open education competencies
Products, outcomes or milestones	Research activities: Instruments application
Name	Appendix 8: Analysis of results e-Open for assessing open education competencies.
Responsible	Yaretzy Gabriela Calamaco Munguia
Research activities	Expert validation of e-Open for assessing open education competencies: An instrument designed within the framework of UNESCO recommendations.

Support evidence:

Application link

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1_y3E2zFMaJjaqVJWnIHU2Kq2t2iHfmtVGcSH873JceY/edit#responses

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdQRP1ApFORSE2ldlakRFzh4_aMdENft3MDerb4iTo4hUSrBA/viewform?usp=header

Analysis per item

Dimensiones	Indicadores	Media
Desarrollo de capacidades	1. Integro recursos educativos abiertos (REA)	2.82
	2. Conozco plataformas virtuales de REA	2.86
	3. Construyo recursos educativos abiertos	2.84
	4. Aplico licencias abiertas como Creative Commons	2.36
	5. Implemento información en múltiples formatos digitales	3.22
	6. Construyo recursos digitales en diferentes formatos	3.18
	7. Conozco y respeto los derechos de autor	3.04
	8. Valoro la educación abierta para desarrollar capacidades tecnológicas	3.25
Elaboración de políticas de apoyo	9. Identifico estándares para protección de datos personales	2.95
	10. Distingo políticas de protección de datos	2.93
	11. Verifico políticas de privacidad	2.91
	12. Diseño marcos regulatorios o políticas de licencias abiertas	2.48
	13. Adopto políticas que promueven la educación abierta	2.77
	14. Valoro el rol de las bibliotecas como promotoras del acceso abierto	3.02
Promoción del acceso efectivo, inclusivo y equitativo	15. Identifico programas de apoyo para sectores vulnerables	2.88
	16. Identifico condiciones para democratizar el conocimiento	3.01
	17. Comparto recursos en plataformas de acceso abierto	2.74
	18. Desarrollo recursos con principios de diseño universal	2.83
	19. Utilizo eficazmente aplicaciones y servicios de Internet	3.19
	20. Priorizo publicar trabajos en acceso abierto	2.41
	21. Valoro participar en proyectos inclusivos	3.24
Creación de modelos de sostenibilidad	22. Identifico modelos de sostenibilidad económica	2.89
	23. Ejecuto proyectos con financiamiento	2.31
	24. Priorizo enfoques de sostenibilidad e inclusión	2.76
	25. Busco vías para proyectos sostenibles	2.79
	26. Identifico oportunidades de financiamiento	2.45
Promoción de la cooperación internacional	27. Utilizo materiales educativos culturalmente diversos	2.98
	28. Opero proyectos de cooperación internacional	2.39
	29. Apoyo acciones de inclusión en redes internacionales	2.72
	30. Valoro participar en redes para promover educación abierta	3.06
Media general	2.87	
Desviación estándar	0.17	
Límite inferior	2.70	
Límite superior	3.05	

Appendix 9: Analysis of results of the instrument on the academic use of Generative AI

Trejo-Trejo, G. A. & Gordillo-Espinoza, E. (n.d.). *Validation of an Instrument to Measure the Academic Use of Generative AI in University Students*. Pixel-Bit. Journal of Media and Education. <https://recyt.fecyt.es/index.php/pixel/article/view/117960/86346>

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 9: Analysis of results Academic use of Generative AI
Products, outcomes or milestones	Research activities: Application and analysis of a validated instrument to identify the academic use of Generative AI among university students.
Name	Appendix 9: Analysis of results Academic use of Generative AI
Responsible	Yovanna Karime Leija Rodriguez
Research activities	To identify and examine the ways in which university students use Generative Artificial Intelligence tools in academic environments, focusing on their use for learning, assignments, information search, and educational support activities.

Support evidence:

<https://forms.gle/CtikqVqGw7ak5mDQA>

Fig. 1. Medias generales por dimensión sobre las percepciones del uso ético de la IAG.

Table 1. Percepciones sobre el uso académico integral y la creación y edición mediante IA

Dimensión	Indicador	Media
Uso académico integral	1. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para buscar información académica.	4.07
	2. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para analizar información de trabajos académicos.	4.11
	3. Uso de IAGen para citar y/o elaborar referencias bibliográficas en formatos diversos.	4.13
	4. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para traducir y comprender textos académicos de otros idiomas.	3.91
	5. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para generar o estructurar ideas, esquemas o argumentos para trabajos académicos.	4.02
	6. Uso de herramientas de IAGen en el día a día para resolver dudas académicas.	3.84
	7. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para revisar gramática, ortografía y estilo en trabajos académicos.	3.88
	8. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para resolver o solicitar ayuda en temas complejos.	3.66
	9. Uso de IAGen como apoyo para prepararse para exámenes.	4.30
Creación y edición	10. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para crear resúmenes de textos académicos.	3.91
	11. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para generar ideas, textos o diapositivas para presentaciones académicas.	4.18
	12. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para redactar y/o editar trabajos académicos.	3.98
	13. Uso de herramientas de IAGen para generar contenido multimedia (videos, imágenes, audio) para utilizarlos en diferentes actividades académicas.	3.93

Table 2 Percepciones sobre la autoeficacia percibida y el uso ético de la IA

Dimensión	Indicador	Media	
Autoeficacia percibida	14. Adaptación y combinación de las respuestas de las herramientas de IAGen con las propias ideas al realizar trabajos académicos.	4.21	
	15. Seguridad al utilizar herramientas de IAGen para la búsqueda de información, redacción de textos o para solución de dudas.	4.14	
	16. Facilidad para aprender a usar nuevas herramientas de IAGen rápidamente si es necesario.	4.16	
	17. Confianza en la capacidad para resolver problemas académicos utilizando herramientas de IAGen.	4.18	
	18. Competencia al utilizar herramientas de IAGen para mejorar mi aprendizaje.	4.14	
	19. Facilidad para utilizar herramientas de IAGen para mejorar la calidad de mis trabajos académicos.	3.96	
	20. Capacidad para evaluar la calidad de la información generada por herramientas de IAGen.	4.23	
	21. Capacidad para integrar herramientas de IAGen de manera efectiva en la rutina de estudio.	4.30	
	Uso ético	22. Comprensión del uso adecuado y ético de las herramientas de IAGen en los estudios.	4.16
		23. Verificación de la confiabilidad de la información y fuentes generadas por las herramientas de IAGen.	4.14
		24. Evaluación del uso de las herramientas de IAGen para la mejora de los aprendizajes.	3.70
25. Consideración de la IAGen como una herramienta complementaria y no como un		3.00	
26. Reconocimiento de que las herramientas de IAGen pueden producir resultados o interpretaciones erróneas.		2.88	
27. Reconocimiento de los riesgos que puede traer el uso de herramientas de IAGen en lo académico.		3.68	
28. Identificación de los riesgos que puede traer el uso de herramientas de IAGen en el ámbito personal.		3.05	

Appendix 10: Webinar Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future

Appendix number & project name - stage	Appendix 10: Webinar Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future
Products, outcomes or milestones	Online presentations and debates on the future of higher education
Name	Appendix 10: Webinar Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future
Responsible	Gabriela Alvarado, Yaretzy Calamaco, Yovanna Leija
Objetive	To foster a global and intercultural dialogue space where students critically analyze the future of education by examining the challenges of the ethical use of artificial intelligence and the integration of open educational resources across different countries, comparing various educational support systems in order to propose collective solutions that transform higher education learning environments.

Support evidence:

<https://www.visioneducativa.mx/webinarfellows-unoe>

Webinar Series Reimagining Learning: Global Student Dialogues for the Future

Organized by UNOE Student Fellows

Objective

To foster a global and intercultural dialogue space where students critically analyze the future of education by examining the challenges of the ethical use of artificial intelligence and the integration of open educational resources across different countries, comparing various educational support systems in order to propose collective solutions that transform higher education learning environments.

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Participating institutions

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